

PREPRINT

Technical Note

Social Network Analysis of Remote Sensing Projects in FP7 with R

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Abstract

The study analysed FP7 projects in the remote sensing using SNA methods. It was performed using R. Based on the data set from CORDIS, an adjacency matrix was constructed and used to plot the network of project participants. Various network indicators were then calculated. In search of notable distributions in network research several statistical methods (maximum likelihood, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, moments, bootstrapping) were used to perform a goodness-of-fit analysis on the frequencies of the degrees, to verify randomness or scale-freedom. The small-world nature was also investigated. The results show that the distribution of the degrees of project participants reflects multiple effects.

remote sensing / project / SNA / FP7 / R

Code (R) and results

Setting of working directory

```
setwd("<working directory")
```

Libraries

```
library(RSQLite)
library(igraph)
library(vcd)
library(powerLaw)
library(fitdistrplus)
```

Creating a formal class to SQLite Connections

```
projects <- dbConnect(RSQLite::SQLite(), "<path>")
```

Creating data frame

```
h2020_participations <- dbGetQuery(projects,
  "SELECT * FROM v_fp7_remote_sensing_project_participants")
```

Number of the occurrences of projects

```
proj_occur <- table(fp7_participations$projectID)
proj_length <- length(proj_occur)
proj_numlist <- vector(mode='list', length=proj_length)
l <- 1
for(l in 1:proj_length){
  proj_numlist [l] <- proj_occur[l]
}
```

Creating project participants' network

```
i <- 0
j <- 0
k <- c()
i_v <- c()
j_v <- c()
z <- c()
for (z in 1:proj_length){
  z_num <- as.numeric(proj_numlist[z])
  j <- j + z_num
  i <- j - z_num + 1
  if(proj_occur[z]!=1){ #1-member projects elimination
    proj_comb <- t(combn(i:j,2))
    proj_comb_length <- length(proj_comb[,1])
    for (pc in 1:proj_comb_length){
      row1 <- proj_comb[pc,1]
      row2 <- proj_comb[pc,2]
      i_v <- append(i_v, fp7_participations[row1, 18])
      j_v <- append(j_v, fp7_participations[row2, 18])
    }
  }
}
```

Creating the graph

```
e1 <- list(i = i_v, j = j_v)
e12 <- matrix(unlist(e1), nrow = length(i_v), ncol = 2)
graph_1 <- graph_from_edgelist(e12, directed = FALSE)
```

Creating the adjacency matrix

```
matrix_adj <- as_adjacency_matrix(graph_1,
  type = "both",
  attr = NULL,
  edges = FALSE,
  names = TRUE,
  sparse = T
)
```

Creating an optimal graph for igraph

```
net <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(
  matrix_adj,
  mode = "min",
  weighted = NULL,
  diag = TRUE,
  add.colnames = NULL,
  add.rownames = NA
)
```

Plot network

```
V(net)$size <- 4
V(net)$frame.color <- "white"
V(net)$color <- "red"
V(net)$label <- ""
E(net)$arrow.mode <- 0
plot(net)
```

Output:

Network measures

```
edge_density(net, loops = F)
transitivity(net, type = "global")
diameter(net, directed = F)
deg <- degree(net, mode = "all")
hist(deg,
  freq = TRUE,
  xlim = range(deg),
  ylim = NULL,
  xlab = "Degree",
  ylab = "Frequency",
  main=""
)
```

Output:

```
[1] 0.04486928
[1] 0.6774518
[1] 6
```


1-5th actors (rcn) by betweenness

```
net.between <- betweenness(net, directed=F, weights=NA)
net.between.sort <- sort(net.between, decreasing = TRUE)
```

```
net.between.sort[1:5]
```

Output:

```
1905609 1949732 1905572 1905912 1930250  
27010.16 15083.31 14733.30 10684.28 9940.00
```

Clusters

```
ceb <- cluster_edge_betweenness(net, directed = FALSE)  
length(ceb)  
plot(ceb, net, vertex.size=3, vertex.label=NA)  
c_vec <- 1:length(ceb)  
for (x in 1:length(ceb)){  
  c_vec[x] <- length(unlist(ceb[x]))  
}  
c_vec  
max(c_vec)
```

Output:

```
[1] 51  
[1] 34 13 4 63 12 11 15 62 21 5 25 6 25 9 6 17 19 5 11 2 14 1 4 3 8 1 15 20 3 2 1  
5 3 18 6 2 1 1  
[39] 2 2 2 3 6 4 16 4 6 4 4 3 1  
[1] 63
```


Goodness of fit analysis of Poisson distribution

```
gf_poisson_deg <- goodfit(deg, type = "poisson", method = "ML")  
summary(gf_poisson_deg)  
rootogram(gf_poisson_deg, xlab = "Degress", ylab = "SQRT(frequencies)")  
unlist(gf_poisson_deg$par)  
gf_poisson_deg$fitted  
gf_poisson_deg$observed  
gf_poisson_deg$count  
gf_poisson_deg$type  
gf_poisson_deg$method  
gf_poisson_deg$df  
gf_poisson_deg$par  
qchisq(p = 0.95, df = gf_poisson_deg$df)
```

Output (partial):

```
Goodness-of-fit test for poisson distribution
      X^2 df P(>X^2)
Likelihood Ratio 6860.88 70 0
```



```
> gf_poisson_deg$df
[1] 70
> gf_poisson_deg$par
$lambda
[1] 23.73585
```

Power distribution goodness of fit analysis

```
power.law.fit(deg, force.continuous = F, implementation = "plfit")
```

Output:

```
$continuous
[1] FALSE
$alpha
[1] 4.326096
$xmin
[1] 68
$logLik
[1] -107.7788
$KS.stat
[1] 0.1005605
$KS.p
[1] 0.9621243
```

Power distribution goodness of fit analysis 2

```
m_pl <- displ$new(deg)
est <- estimate_xmin(m_pl)
est
m_pl$setXmin(est)
bs <- bootstrap(m_pl, no_of_sims = 500, threads = 2)
plot(bs, trim = 0.1)
bs_p <- bootstrap_p(m_pl, no_of_sims = 500, threads = 2)
bs_p
bs_p$x
plot(bs_p, trim = 0.1)
bs_p$bootstraps
```

Output (partial):

```
$gof
[1] 0.1018532
$xmin
```

```

[1] 68
$pars
[1] 4.326065
$ntail
[1] 25
$distance
[1] "ks"
attr(,"class")
[1] "estimate_xmin"

```



```

$p
[1] 0.564
$gof
[1] 0.1018532
$sim_time
[1] 1.343084
$distance
[1] "ks"
attr(,"class")
[1] "bs_p_xmin"

```


Skewness and kurtosis

```
plotdist(deg, histo = T, demp = T, discrete = T)
```

```
descdist(deg, boot = 1000)
```

```
descdist(deg, discrete = T, boot = 1000)
```

Output:

summary statistics

```
min: 1 max: 196
```

```
median: 17
```

```
mean: 23.73585
```

```
estimated sd: 22.08863
```

```
estimated skewness: 2.816406
```

```
estimated kurtosis: 15.66522
```

Cullen and Frey graph

summary statistics

```

-----
min: 1  max: 196
median: 17
mean: 23.73585
estimated sd: 22.08863
estimated skewness: 2.816406
estimated kurtosis: 15.66522
    
```

Cullen and Frey graph

Sources

Zsolt Tóth. (2022). Dataset of FP7 projects related to remote sensing [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7099646>

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